

Psychological Security in the University Educational Environment

Armine Vazgen Vahanyan¹

Received: 11 May 2022 / Accepted: 30 May 2022 / Published: 24 November 2022

© 2022 Vazgen Vahanyan Armine

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8154312

Abstract

The psychological security of the educational environment is considered to be one of the most important preconditions, which allows to give a developing character to the system. Therefore, it is important to formulate its ensuring goals and principles. The concept of psychological security of the educational environment is a system of measures ensuring mental health of the subject's in the conditions of pedagogical cooperation. This system is formulated on the basis of theoretical analysis, as a result of which: a) "educational environment" (psychological aspect) and b) "psychological security" are being defined. Conclusion on considering one of the social institutions included in the provision of national security (social aspect) is being substantiated. Main threats that destabilize psychological security in the educational environment are being detected. The category of psychological security is defined by us in three aspects: 1) environment and ensuring mental health of the participants involved as a system of interpersonal relationships that gives participants a sense of belonging (environmental referentiality function); 2) absence of social-psychological threats. convince the person that he/she is out of danger; 3) improvement of a person's mental health. The modeling of psychological security in the educational environment should be based on the following principles: a) principle of relying on developing education; b) principle of psychological protection of the individual (support for the development of social-psychological skills of the individual).

Keywords: psychological security, educational environment, mental

¹ Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Yerevan HAYBUSAK University, Email: a.v.vahanyan@gmail.com

Introduction

The modeling of psychological security in the educational environment should be based on the following principles: • Principle of reliance on developmental education, • Principle of psychological protection of the individual, • Principle of support for the development of a person's social-psychological skills. One of the most important mechanisms for the socialization of a person is education, which can be presented in terms of the level of achievement of goals.

2. Literature Review

The priorities of youth education and professional training are reflected in the prism of breaking public interests. In modern psycho-pedagogical science, education is considered in several aspects: as an educational system, as an educational process, as an educational activity, as an individual or cumulative result of a process, as an educational environment. The social quality of the educational environment is conditioned by the peculiarities of the relations in the system. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in studying the socio-psychological environment of individuals. Levin, in his field theory, clearly presents man's relationship with the environment. In his scheme, which determines the position of man in the world around him, three basic concepts are used: «the person» (the person, P), «psychological environment» (environment, E), and «physical world» or «non-psychological world» («physical world», PW). His main thesis is the recognition of the unity of a specific subject and a certain environment. The subject together with its internal individual systems and psychological field («living space») forms a unified continuity. Levin believed, that events occurring in psychological environment could cause changes in physical world, and vice versa. Accordingly, there is an interaction between person and psychological environment. In order to understand the motives of a person's activity, it is necessary to observe the organism in conditions of constant interaction with the environment. The environment plays a dual role. First of all, it acts as a source of information that allows a person to predict the consequences of possible alternative actions. Second, it is the reality where human activity is organized. Maslow divides the environment into geographical and psychological. Psychology arises when a person presents relevant psychological needs. (Maslow, 2001 Motivation and personality; ST. P) The interdependence of a man with the environment is considered within the framework of existential psychology, which is reflected in the basic concept

of being "in the world" (Dasein). This means that people do not exist separately from the world, and the world does not exist apart from humans (Лэнгле А., Person, 2008, 159 с.)
Экзистенциально-аналитическая теория личности: Сборник статей: Пер. с немец. м. /Вступ.ст. С.В. Кривцовой. М., Генезис Франкл В., Человек в поисках смысла;. (1990, 368 с.) Сборник: Пер. с англ. и нем. /Общ. ред. Л. Я. Гозмана и Д. А. Леонтьева, Прогресс, М.,].

Humanistic psychology, which views education as a system that develops personality, the main source of human development discovers the driving force in the system of individual. The need for security is one of the foundations in the hierarchy of personal needs (Maslow A. 2001) Motivation and personality; ST. P), without which satisfaction is impossible to achieve self-realization (Maslow, 2001) Motivation and personality; ST. P). It is difficult to maintain mental health if one does not understand the connection between self-preservation and developmental opportunities. According to Maslow, the conflict between these phenomena is existential, rooted in the depths of human nature.

The phenomenon of psychological security: The educational environment would be incomplete if the conditions necessary for fully discovering the human potential were not defined. We believe that the whole of these conditions can be defined as "psychological security".

The term "psychological security" applies to all areas of human life, hence the educational environment is also involved. The concept of psychological security is used in various subject areas related to the professional activities of people. In the early stages of development, the social conditions of the participants' interaction in the educational environment occupy a leading place. We consider the psychological security of the educational environment to be the most important condition that provides an opportunity to give a developing nature to the educational environment. Therefore, it is significant to formulate the conceptual provisions, goals and principles of its creation. The concept of psychological security of the educational environment is an existing system for ensuring the positive development of subjects and mental health in the conditions of pedagogical cooperation. The latter is formulated on the basis of theoretical analysis, as a result of which:

- "educational environment" (psychological aspect) and "psychological security" notions are defined.
- The conclusion on the possibility of considering the high school as one of the social institutions included in the provision of national security (social side) is being substantiated.

The revealed functions and structure of the educational environment require analytical evaluation and comparison of two closely related concepts.

1. The social-psychological atmosphere of the professional group and the psychological characteristics of the educational environment;
2. The nature and ways of the interaction of the subjects (social or communication component).

Let us consider the main provisions and concepts of psychological security of the educational environment. Education is a sphere of social "production". This means that the higher education institutions, as non-governmental organizations producing "super-complex products", must create stable conditions for "production" and use technologies that have the least risk of harming the development of the individual, as well as development opportunities. In terms of psychology, we can say that if in an authoritarian system public institution (including the school) were created to control man, then in the humanistic paradigm man is given a "basic sense of satisfaction" (Маслоу, 1982, pp. 1). In this regard, education and psychological support should be at the epicenter of the educational institution's activity.

1. Educational environment as part of the educational area.

The educational environment has a territorial allocation and other qualitative characteristics that allow to fully meet the needs of young people for development, socialization, and cultural identification while ensuring their safety. The educational system, which includes separate educational institutions, the psychological essence of which is the creation of conditions and opportunities for maintaining the psychological security of the educational environment, act as an organizational structure ensuring the solution of these problems. Through the educational policy, a common educational area is created, aimed at maintaining and strengthening the physical, mental, and social health of the person. In a psychological sense, this is the creation and

introduction of technologies to support the psychological security of the educational environment.

2. Threats to the psychological security of the educational environment. The main threat to the interaction of the beneficiaries of the educational environment is psychological trauma, which results in damage to positive development and mental health, the basic needs of the person are not met, i.e. there is a barrier to self-realization. The main source of psychological trauma is psychological violence in the joint process of interaction. The analysis of the works on the problems of psychological violence gives grounds to distinguish the following manifestations: public humiliation, insult, ridicule, threat, insulting name, compulsion to act against one's own will, neglect, disrespectful attitude, unfriendly attitude. The criterion for the absence of this threat will be an adequate assessment of the psychological protection of all participants in the educational environment.

A factor threatening psychological security is that the group members do not recognize the referential significance of the educational environment, and as a result of the intention to leave it or the actual denial of its values and norms. (Баева И. А. Б., (2002. — 271 с.) Психологическая безопасность в образовании: Монография. — СПб.: Издательство «СОЮЗ» Костина Л. М., Психологическая безопасность личности: подходы, компоненты/ Преемственность психологической науки в России: традиции и инновации: (2012.) материалов Международной научно- практической конференции, посвященной 215-летию РГПУ им. А. И. Герцена, /rustudent.com/psihologicheskaya-bezopasnostlichnosti-podhodyi-komp...). Thus, another criterion of psychological security of the educational environment is its referentiality, fixed as a positive, neutral or negative attitude.

3. This criterion of psychological security of the educational environment is the level of satisfaction with the main characteristics of the interaction process.

A threat to psychological security is also the lack of satisfaction with the basic characteristics of the interaction process of all participants in the educational environment. The empirical manifestations here are the following: emotional comfort, opportunity to express an opinion, respect for oneself, preservation of personal dignity, ability to seek help, discussion of personal problems and difficulties, attention to requests and suggestions, mutual help.

Organizationally threatening to the health of the participants of the educational environment is the underdevelopment of the psychological support system, the inefficiency of the support

service in the educational system. This implies a large-scale task of eliminating the threats listed in the educational environment, which will help to reduce psychological risks both in the educational space and, more broadly, through the spread of secure relationships between participants in social life.

3. Results

Ensuring psychological security of the educational environment.

In the educational system, the priority for the support service should be the provision of psychological security of the educational environment, as a consequence, the protection of the mental health of its participants. In order to ensure psychological security in the educational environment, it is necessary to rely on a number of principles. The principle of relying on developmental education, the main purpose of which is not education, but the harmonious development of the individual's consciousness, physical, emotional, intellectual, social and caring spheres [Вачков И.В. Смена (2000. N4) Приоритетов//Школьный психолог; Панов В.И. (2000). Экопсихология.М.]. The basis of such an educational process is not the logic of influence, but the logic of interaction.

The second principle, based on which it is necessary to design a psychologically safe educational environment is the principle of psychological protection of a person from each subject of the educational process. The implementation of this principle in interaction is the elimination of psychological violence. Vulnerable people should receive resources, psychological support, and protection of the right to safe cooperation.

Support for the development of social-psychological skills.

Informative support - professional advice, situation analysis, feedback, information, that helps solve raised problems. Status support – acceptance, approval, respect, provision of positive social comparison, support for the growth of the subject's self-esteem, information necessary for the expression of self-esteem, recognition of the individual. Instrumental support - services, material and practical assistance for the achievement of a goal, solution of a problem, management of a crisis and etc.

Social-psychological skills enable a person to choose his / her way of life competently, to solve problems independently, to analyze the situation and to choose appropriate behavior, that does not violate the freedom and dignity of others, excludes psychological violence and triggers self-development of a person. It is crucial that the world is predictable, organized, as it creates a sense of security.

Today, in many studies and discussions on the issue of the new psychological-pedagogical quality of the educational process, two poles can be mentioned. The first is the persistent introduction of the ideas of humanism as a basic and mandatory condition. Relationships between subjects of education (often quite declaratively expressed as love for children, attention to emotions, pursuing of needs and etc.). The second is to rely on ready-made learning technologies (usually 1920 developing), where there is a clear regulation of interaction, as well as a step- by-step technological sequence. This structural model can be used as a basis for the development of psychological support programs and technologies for the subjects of the educational process in order to create psychological security in the educational environment of a high school. The horizontal direction can be related to the development task of the individual, and the vertical direction to its development. The provision of psychological resources in both directions, which allows for creating psychological security in the educational environment, is the primary issue of the support service.

It is proposed to create an operational structural model in the educational environment of the university, which allows to develop technologies in order to ensure the psychological security of subjects. The psychological service in a high school will allow to maintain and strengthen the level of mental health, and psychological well-being, improve the quality of life of both university students and teaching staff, ensure the existence of psychological culture and intergenerational tolerance, promote early detection of personal and social problems, as well as the formation of social and family values among young people.

References

- Lewin, K. (1961). *Fieldtheory in social science*. N.Y. Maslow, A. (;2001) *Motivation and personality*; ST. P
- Баева, И. А. Б., (2002. — 271 с.) *Психологическая безопасность в образовании: Монография.* — СПб.: Издательство «СОЮЗ»
- Вачков, И.В. Смена (2000. N4) *Приоритетов//Школьный психолог* Костина Л. М., *Психологическая безопасность личности: подходы, компоненты/ Преимственность психологической науки в России: традиции и инновации: (2012.) материалов Международной научно-практической конференции, посвященной 215-летию РГПУ им. А. И. Герцена, /rstudent.com/psihologicheskaya-bezopasnostlichnosti-podhodyi- komp.../,*
- Лэнгле, А. *Person: (2008, 159 с.) Экзистенциально-аналитическая теория личности: Сборник статей: Пер. с немец. м. /Вступ.ст. С.В. Кривцовой. М., Генезис*
- Маслоу, А. (1982). *Самоактуализация//Психология личности;Тексты Панов В.И. (2000). Экопсихология.М.Франкл В., Человек в поисках смысла; (1990, 368 с.) Сборник: Пер. с англ. и нем. /Общ. ред. Л. Я. Гозмана и Д. А. Леонтьева, Прогресс, М.,*
- Фромм Э., (1998.) *Здоровое общество / Фромм Э. Мужчина и женщина, М., Անձի հոգեբանական անվտանգության հիմնախնդիրը. Կոլեկտիվ մենագրություն: (2009, 164 էջ). Հեղ. Ռ. Վ. Ադոլֆսոնյան, Ս. Ս. Ամիրյան, Վ. Ռ. Պապոյան և ուրիշներ, Եր., ԵՊՀ հրատ.*